

DIDACTIC OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10500217>

Abstract. *This article talks about didactics of formation of professional competencies of future teachers in educational institutions.*

Keywords: *educational institutions, competence, pedagogical technologies, new approach, communicative competence, experience, professional tasks, psychological capabilities of the subject, psychological knowledge, motivational characteristics, pedagogue's professionalism, pedagogical skill, individual image of the pedagogue, efficiency of activity.*

At present, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system, the development of democratization and humanization processes require a new approach to modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

The term "pedagogical technologies" is based on the concepts of "technology", "technological process". These concepts mean a technical document about the sequence of work performed to obtain a finished product in industry, and a complex of methodological activities in science in education. Currently, the main way to understand pedagogical technology is to focus on clearly defined goals, to establish regular interaction with the learner, and to teach through the behavior of the learner, which is the philosophical basis of pedagogical technology. Interaction forms the basis of pedagogical technology and should fully cover the educational process, technology as a complex process consists of a number of teaching stages, and each of these stages, in turn, consists of specific actions. Practice is the sum of the work done by the teacher in the classroom in terms of explaining the learning elements on the subject, and it is the completed part of the teaching process at this stage.

The professional pedagogical activity of the teacher is carried out on the basis of "teacher-student" interaction, in this process educational, educational, correctional, developmental and formative goals are realized. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay attention to communicative (dialogue) competence when studying the professional-psychological competence of a future teacher. In modern psychology, there are several approaches to the study of communicative competence and the conditions and factors of its formation. For example, representatives of the behaviorist direction define communicative competence as a person's ability to demonstrate appropriate behavior in certain situations, to rationally assess the situation and to act accordingly. Supporters of the direction of cognitive psychology believe that communicative competence is formed directly depending on the level of the subject's cognitive field, his knowledge of human psychology, as well as his social thinking, imagination and perception. Another important component of the general structure of professional psychological competence in pedagogical activities is social competence, because a modern teacher not only provides knowledge, information, and information to students, but also acts as a mediator between a developing person and society. The appropriateness of "child-society" relations and interaction also depends on how competent and influential the teacher is in social life. Among the main functions of social competence, it is possible to include concepts such as adaptation, social orientation, and the

combination of personal and social experiences. The level of social competence of a person is important in the process of establishing mutual communication and activities. At the same time, according to the results of the research conducted by psychologists, the formation of the level of social competence in people is of special importance in the process of adaptation of citizens to the new social and globalization conditions. Environmental, political, ideological, and social changes not only determine the development of social thinking, but also affect people's self-awareness, life values, and personal problems. This puts before the science of psychology the task of creating programs aimed at improving the level of competence of a person in solving problems related to socialization and social adaptation. In our opinion, this task is particularly relevant to the work of pedagogues, who are responsible for the formation of not only themselves, but also their students as well-rounded individuals.

Social competence occupies an important place among the various forms of psychological competence studied by modern psychology. It also reflects the creative features of a person as a subject of social mutual partnership and cooperation. Interest in the mechanisms of the subject's competence social behavior formation, manifestation tendencies, motivation, and content is characterized, first of all, by the influence of the character of "human-society" interaction on social progress and development.

Since competence is a unique structural characteristic of a person, psychologists emphasize another component of this structure - self-competence. In modern psychology, self-competence is a category that means that the subject is ready to change his/her personality traits and behavioral skills in a purposeful way, to use his/her mental resources wisely, and has the potential for this. Auto-competence includes effective assimilation of new knowledge, information, high-level self-control skills and competencies, and independent formation of voluntary guidelines for success. At the same time, the ability of an individual to create a comfortable, acceptable situation and conditions by changing his internal state when extreme, unforeseen situations arise in the course of his life is an example of auto-competence. Thus, auto-competence is a quality of a person, which is formed in certain periods of a person's life and allows to effectively engage in a certain type of activity.

The results of the analysis of psychological competence indicate that it is a complex psychological structure consisting of a system and interrelated features. Under the concept of psychological competence, professional and personal qualities that help to positively solve the problems that a person may encounter during his professional activity and life are understood. The teacher's psychological competence has substantive and technological aspects and develops in the process of assimilation of information related to various specializations and specialties.

The problem of the development of human psychological competence in the science of psychology from different perspectives (cause and effect; directions and trends in the development of competence in the achievement of professional skills; the interaction of internal and external conditions in the achievement of a high level of competence; criteria and measurements of the level of development of psychological competence) has been analyzed.

It has been proven in studies that the psychological readiness and readiness of future teachers for the formation of competence is the reason for this aspect to be formed faster and more effectively. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the stimulation of readiness for competence in future pedagogues.

From a psychological point of view, there are motivational, emotional, moral, cognitive and behavioral levels of preparation. Activation of preparation occurs only when these levels are interrelated, understood and perceived by a person. Psychological preparation can be described as a complex dynamic structure that includes the following aspects:

- understanding of individual needs and requirements, professional tasks specific to the subject of pedagogical activity;
- understanding the goals of competence development;
- to evaluate and understand the conditions under which activity is manifested, the experience related to the performance of a certain task, recall;
- to find the most optimal methods and tools for performing tasks within the framework of personal experience analysis and psychological capabilities, self-control.

Internal and external conditions can include:

- novelty, relevance, motivation for creativity, content, level of complexity of educational tasks;
- behavioral characteristics of people around;
- specific aspects of the system of support and encouragement of active actions and results;
- level of aspirations and motivation for success;
- assessment of the subject's own readiness and psychological capabilities, as well as necessary willpower;
- the ability to create and support a positive psychological climate and environment at various stages of work on improving one's competence.

Many opinions have been expressed about the fact that the development of professional psychological competence depends not only on the volume and quantity of psychological knowledge, skills and abilities, but also on the subject's aspirations to master and implement a model of competent professional behavior. In this, the character of a certain individual subject, the direction of values, the way of thinking, worldview, beliefs, ideals, self-concept, self-awareness, and the motivation of a person to become competent plays an important role. In particular, the content of motivational characteristics is important in determining the effectiveness of competence.

At this point, it is necessary to pay attention to the aspirations of a person to develop his professional and personal qualities. The analysis of scientific-theoretical literature in the field of motivational psychology dedicated to the study of the development of professional qualities of a person testifies that there are many types of motivational inclinations involved in the management and control of this process. The following sociogenic, socially important needs also play a role in the subject's professional and personal development: self-expression, self-activation, creative growth, professional guidance, as well as internal and extrinsic activity motives. These needs serve as a unique motivational background in the process of personal professionalization.

The process of competence development is individual and unique to each person. Some people pay attention to content components, they are primarily interested in theoretical psychological data. This ensures that they are psychologically literate, but does not allow them to have competent behavior. The same people try hard to learn psychological methods, tools, secrets of interaction, but they do not pay attention to their theoretical foundations. This is like a person who knows how to drive a car superficially, but is not fully aware of its structure, management rules and principles, is not considered a good driver.

And finally, there is another group of people who are able to use their psychological knowledge, which they have carefully acquired, in any situation as appropriate as possible, and are constantly developing their psychological professional competence.

We believe that it is necessary for a teacher not only to feel competent in the course of his pedagogical activity, but also to demonstrate and prove this quality to others. He should be recognized as a competent specialist. The modern concept of education emphasizes and pays attention to this aspect.

Thus, in real situations, in pedagogical processes, the teacher's competence can have an appropriate effect on the student and create a positive motivation in him, or, on the contrary, it can act as a psychological brake and prevent the development of the child's competence.

So, competence as a broad concept means the theoretical and practical readiness of the teacher to perform his professional and professional duties, and as a subject to correctly manage his relations with the outside world and people, education. It is one of the important tasks before us to decide on this feature in the process.

The professional identity of the future teacher requires a constructive-transformative attitude towards professional activity, it is reflected in the subjective and objective results of labor activity, educational work with students is meaningful, technologically educational. It is manifested in a specific, purposeful organization.

The professional identity of a future teacher as a complex integrative structure includes the following components:

axiological (sympathetic to personal creative initiatives in professional-pedagogical activity; use of innovative methods from a professional-practical point of view in raising and teaching the younger generation; all creative and positive ways of solving professional problems in teaching students search for productive opportunities);

professional-gnostic (solving professional-pedagogical and creative tasks, mastering the methodology of educating the younger generation, mastering the theory and technology of performing socio-cultural tasks; the ability to systematically analyze professional tasks, possessing developed creative thinking);

emotional-perceptive (empathy, sympathy, intuition; the specialist's ability to feel and control his emotional state);

creative-processual (the ability to understand and solve a professional problem related to the creation of original pedagogical technology; the ability to independently plan and implement one's own activities; a new approach that raises professional activity to a higher level and achieves positive results in the field of education of the younger generation suggest ideas, etc.).

In this research work, the concept of "individual image of a pedagogue" is defined as the integration of psychological-pedagogical, verbal and non-verbal characteristics necessary for the effective implementation of the activity in the image of a specific specialist.

On the one hand, the professionalism of the teacher is seen as a determinant of achieving high performance, and on the other hand, as a dynamic system developing in professional activity.

As a result of the analysis of relevant philosophical, psychological, pedagogical and sociological researches, we came to the following conclusion: the professionalism of a pedagogue is a systematic and integrated description of a person, which includes pedagogical competence, pedagogical skills, aspects that reflect the individual image of the pedagogue and its unique characteristics, and the effectiveness of the activity, ensures efficiency.

It is desirable to form the individuality and uniqueness of the future pedagogue (student) in the following directions: firstly, in the process of mastering general theoretical subjects, the student tries to take the position of the subject of understanding, in which, for example, the acquired knowledge, skills and seeks to understand the relationship between their qualifications and their future occupation. Secondly, in the process of theoretical and practical professional training, the student feels himself as a pedagogue and tries to create his own position without being influenced by theoretical templates. Theoretical and methodical sciences serve as the initial basis for such a student. The student should strive to develop his own methods for solving educational tasks.

It should be noted that the formation and development of the student's individuality should be directed to the reform of the motivational sphere. In this case, guidelines for achieving specific achievements should be shown for the student during his educational activities. Therefore, the formation of individuality is a long process and may consist of several stages. The number and duration of stages are different for each person (student).

It is desirable to present several ways and methods of mastering educational standards for the formation of an individual style of pedagogical activity among students of higher education organizations.

We believe that the following tasks should be carried out for the formation of an individual style of pedagogical activity in the system of professional pedagogical education:

carrying out exercises to develop empathy, pedagogical reflection and pedagogical communication;

participation in classes of students from other groups;

study of advanced pedagogical practices;

getting rid of various pedagogical stereotypes.

Professionalization in a pedagogical higher education organization includes:

1. A person's feeling in a new educational environment.
2. Realization of one's capabilities in the process of mastering the methodology, theory and technology of pedagogical activity.
3. Orientation to acquire professional functions based on one's capabilities.
4. Striving for self-expression in pedagogical activity with various methods and tools.

Students should acquire new knowledge and creative experiences in order to form an individual style of pedagogical activity in a higher education organization in the field of pedagogy. In order for students to better imagine the various forms of these methods, professors and teachers need to demonstrate individual methods of pedagogical activity. Also, for the formation of an individual style of pedagogical activity in students, it is important to have education in a dialogical form and to have the skills of independent work. The training program on the model of constructive behavior change proposed by L. Mitina within the scope of the researched topic is very noteworthy.

The formation of an individual style of pedagogical activity depends not only on externally controlled influences, but also on the individual's self-development and professional improvement. Therefore, it is appropriate to talk about the formation of the foundations of an individual style in the process of professional training in a higher education organization. The foundations of the individual style of the pedagogue summarize social, general cultural, special-subject and psychological-pedagogical preparation for professional activity.

The stages of development of professional individuality are as follows:

pre-professional and initial professional stage;

the stage of professional formation of the basic level of behavior in society and the possibilities of its reflection;

the stage of formation of basic professional behavior and its reflection;

professional self-awareness and improvement of professional skills - the stage of organizing one's professional activity and developing professional identity.

At each stage, it is desirable to develop the subject-specific, personality and individual characteristics of the students, to develop the necessary qualities in interaction with the students. At the same time, it is necessary to direct the tools of pedagogical influence used in the training system to the development of appropriate professional and personal qualities in students.

Pedagogical skill is a qualitative characteristic of the subject of activity related to mastering pedagogical skills, verbal and non-verbal communication, emotional-volitional self-management techniques.

The model of the process of formation of the professional individuality of a pedagogue in the context of a higher education organization includes the following interrelated modules:

diagnostic (set of methods and forms of diagnostics of students' needs, professional and personal interests, creative potential);

prognostic (determining the individual professional-educational direction of students, taking into account personal characteristics and prospects of professional-professional growth; determining the system of variable forms of psychological-pedagogical and consultative-methodological support for graduates of higher education institutions);

substantive-technological (a set of variable-differential and substantive modules necessary for the professional training of a future teacher;

textual, practical-oriented, problem-related, project, heuristic technologies of professional training, etc.);

related to monitoring (internal and external complex system of evaluating the effectiveness of the development of the future teacher's professional identity; motivational-valuable, creative-cognitive, emotional-perceptive, creative- a set of performance criteria).

In the educational process, it is recommended to use a personal-oriented model that helps to implement the mutual relations between professors and students in order to form professional individuality in students. This model assumes that in the attitude of the teacher to the student, he should pay attention to the potential of the individual, make decisions independently and take responsibility for the result, as a priority.

The readiness to form an innovative individual style of activity, to generalize one's own and colleagues' experience, and to reflect is one of the important conditions for the formation of the professional individuality of a specialist.

The following can be included in the set of conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the process of forming the professional individuality of a pedagogue in the conditions of a higher education organization:

organizational and administrative conditions;

didactic-technological conditions (clarification of mutual structural-logical relations of educational subjects in the study of various aspects of the professional-personal development of the future teacher; the possibility of acquiring several specialties of students in the conditions of a higher education organization; future improving the content of specialized subjects, higher

education organization curricula, programs, taking into account the specification of the professional activity of the teacher, the prospective and current needs of the labor market, the requests of employers of a certain region, the individual characteristics of students; the higher education organization establishing a methodical system for developing students' creative thinking during the educational process, focusing on learning and practical activities);

socio-pedagogical conditions (implementation of pedagogical tutoring technologies, facilitator activities by professors and teachers of higher educational institutions and methodologists of pedagogical practice; scientists who conduct expertise of projects of future teachers in the implementation of professional-pedagogical initiatives of students establishing cooperation with; conducting continuous pedagogical monitoring of the dynamics of formation of the future teacher's professional individuality and professional-creative activity).

In general, in the process of mastering professional skills, in the formation of students' motivation for professional-pedagogical activity, appropriate pedagogical principles, approaches, pedagogical conditions, forms, methods and methods of teaching, effective use of teaching tools in improving the training of pedagogical staff is important.

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